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АНАЛИЗ ЭФФЕКТА СМЕЩЕНИЯ ЯДРА ОТ ГЕОМЕТРИЧЕСКОГО ЦЕНТРА СПИРАЛЬНОЙ ГАЛАКТИКИ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Для анализа физики образования галактик и других гравитационных систем сначала необходимо создать для них точные аналитически решаемые модели. С учетом этого были созданы новые аналитические модели и найдены критические диаграммы, образующие аналоги нелинейных нестационарных уравнений для моды (1;3), соответствующей смещению ядра от геометрического центра, которое находится на фоне спиральных галактик.

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SPIRAL GALAKTIKALARNING GEOMETRIK MARKAZIDAN YADRONING SILJISHI TA'SIRINI TAHLIL QILISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Galaktikalar va boshqa gravitatsion sistemalarning shakllanish fizikasini tahlil qilish uchun bizga birinchi navbatda, ular uchun aniq analitik yechiladigan modellar tuzish zarur. Shuni hisobga olgan holda yangi analitik modellar tuzilib, ular fonida spiral galaktikalarda uchraydigan yadroni geometrik markazdan siljishiga javob beradigan (1;3) moda uchun nohiziqli nostatsionar tenglamalar analogini hosil qilib kritik diagramalari topildi.

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ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECT OF DISPLACEMENT OF THE CORE FROM THE GEOMETRIC CENTER OF SPIRAL GALAXIES

ANNOTATION

To analyze the physics of the formation of galaxies and other gravitational systems, we first need to create accurate analytically solvable models for them. Taking this into account, new analytical models were created, and critical diagrams were found, forming analogs of nonlinear non-stationary equations for the (1;3) mode, which corresponds to the displacement of the nucleus from the geometric center, which occurs in spiral galaxies.

1. Introduction.

According to astrophysical and radio astronomical observations, the distribution of neutral hydrogen HI and stars in many cases are "lopsided" [1-4]. Such a structure in galaxies was first noted in [5]. It has been shown that the proportion of lopsided structures in galaxies can reach 50% or more [6–10]. Therefore, lopsided can have a significant effect on the evolution of the galaxy [11]. A high proportion of galaxies exhibiting lopsided indicates that it is quite stable over a long period of time [12]. Many authors have analyzed images of galaxies in the near-IR range and characterized the asymmetry using the Fourier analysis method. In particular, since the $m=1$ mode does not have an internal Lindblad resonance, this mode makes it possible to transport matter to the central region [13]. Thus, the skew can affect star formation and play a potential role in fueling the nuclear region [14]. A variety of physical mechanisms have also been identified that can induce a one-way shift in a disk galaxy. For example, the reaction of a disk to a one-sided halo due to tidal interactions [15], or a merger of satellite galaxies [16] or a tidal collision [17, 18] and asymmetric gas accretion [17] can lead to the excitation of a one-sided mode $m=1$. Many authors have tried to process observational data in order to determine the value of the A1 coefficient [19, 20] by analyzing the corresponding Fourier harmonic.

It is known from the values of the Fourier coefficient that the lopsoidality of the structure is currently the largest fraction in spiral galaxies [21]. Until the 1990s, in the world literature, the formation of a large-scale structure of galaxies was studied within the framework of equilibrium models [22-28], which are unable to explain the observational data regarding the non-linear non-stationary stage of the evolution of self-gravitating systems. On the other hand, foreign authors studied the problems of the origin of large-scale structures using numerical experiments [29-32], setting at the initial moment various degrees of nonequilibrium, due to which results were obtained that reproduce the phenomenon of observed structures in real astrophysical systems. However, in numerical experiments it is impossible to determine the physical mechanism leading to a new observed state and to see possible nonlinear phenomena, resonance processes and the nature of gravitational instabilities that took place during the experiment. The shortcomings of the above models were first taken into account in the analytical models of the authors [33–36], where non-linear nonstationary pulsating models with rotation were constructed on the basis of equilibrium models, describing the initial stages of the formation of self-gravitating systems. Note that at the beginning, non-rotating pulsating versions of equilibrium models of self-gravitating systems were constructed, and then the problems of their stability were investigated. We have also investigated the formation of a lopsaidal structure in self-gravity systems by forming one of these models. We have obtained non-stationary dispersion equations against the background of a non-equilibrium model, found the corresponding solutions by numerical methods, and obtained the necessary dependence diagrams. This will help us understand how real disks evolve and how fast these processes go.

2 . Basic formulas and ratios.

Nuritdinov [33] constructed an isotropic model for the distribution of matter in a non-stationary disk

$$\Psi_i(r, v_r, v_{\perp}, t) = \frac{\sigma_0}{2\pi\sqrt{1-\Omega^2}} \left[\frac{1-\Omega^2}{\Pi^2} \left(1 - \frac{r^2}{\Pi^2} \right) - (v_r - v_a)^2 - (v_{\perp} - v_b)^2 \right]^{-1/2} \chi(R-r), \tag{1}$$

where the pulsation occurs in the radial direction $R(t) = R_0 \Pi(t)$, moreover $\Pi(t) = \frac{1 + \lambda \cos \Psi}{1 - \lambda^2}$, time $t = \frac{\Psi + \lambda \sin \Psi}{(1 - \lambda^2)^{3/2}}$. The following normalization is performed $\pi^2 G \sigma_0 = 2R_0$ ($R_0 = 1$), the parameter Ω represents the rotation of the disk ($0 \leq \Omega \leq 1$), and χ - is the Heaviside function. The amplitude of disk pulsations in the radial direction is $\lambda = 1 - (2T/|U|)_0$, and the range of its change is : $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$. The equilibrium position at $\lambda=0$ corresponds to the Bisnovaty-Kogan-Zeldovich model. This case has been studied by many authors [22-28].

The surface density of the disk (1) is equal to

$$\sigma(\vec{r}, t) = \frac{\sigma_0}{\Pi^2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{r^2}{R^2}}. \tag{2}$$

The non-linear non-stationary model (1) is isotropic in terms of the velocity components, just like the equilibrium model. Since this model (1) was somewhat ideal, it was necessary to create an anisotropic

model. To create an anisotropic model, a new model was built by averaging an isotropic model under certain conditions [33] using a weight function for the selected rotation parameter

$$\Psi_a = \frac{\int_{-1}^{+1} \rho(\Omega) \cdot \Psi \, d\Omega}{\int_{-1}^{+1} \rho(\Omega) \, d\Omega}, \tag{3}$$

the form of the weight function chosen by us $\rho(\Omega) = \frac{8}{\pi} \cdot \Omega^2 \cdot \sqrt{1 - \Omega^2}$. Our weight function must satisfy the following normalization condition $\int_{-1}^1 \rho(\Omega) \, d\Omega = 1$. Integral form of the distribution function

$$\Psi_a(r, v_r, v_{\perp}) = \frac{4 \cdot \sigma_0}{\pi^2} \int_{-\sqrt{D}}^{\sqrt{D}} \frac{(X+r \cdot v_{\perp})^2}{\sqrt{D-X^2}} \, dX. \tag{4}$$

Here $D = (1 - \frac{r^2}{\pi^2})(1 - \Pi^2 \cdot v_{\perp}^2) - \Pi^2(v_r - v_a)^2 \geq 0$ and $\Omega \cdot r \cdot v_{\perp} = X$. The algebraic representation of the distribution function has the form

$$\Psi_a(r, v_r, v_{\perp}, t) = \frac{2 \cdot \sigma_0}{\pi} \cdot \left(2 \cdot r^2 \cdot v_{\perp}^2 + \left(1 - \frac{r^2}{\pi^2} \right) (1 - \Pi^2 v_{\perp}^2) - \Pi^2 (v_r^2 - v_{\perp}^2)^2 \right) \chi \left(\left(1 - \frac{r^2}{\pi^2} \right) (1 - \Pi^2 v_{\perp}^2) - \Pi^2 (v_r^2 - v_{\perp}^2)^2 \right). \tag{5}$$

The isotropic (1) and anisotropic (5) models can be linearly related according to the superposition principle. We created a composite model using this principle:

$$\Psi_s(r, v_r, v_{\perp}, v, t) = v \cdot \Psi_i(r, v_r, v_{\perp}, t) + (1-v) \cdot \Psi_a(r, v_r, v_{\perp}, t). \tag{6}$$

When using the principle of linear superposition, a new variable superposition parameter v is introduced. Here the superposition parameter v varies in the range $0 \leq v \leq 1$. The composite model allows one to study the processes occurring in intermediate models between (1) and (5) within the same model.

3. Instability of the lopsided mode for a composite model.

Since we are primarily interested in the displacement of the core, below we consider the oscillation modes of the azimuthal wave number $m=1$ and the radial wave number $N=3$. The instability of this oscillation mode leads to a displacement of the kinematic center of the system [25]. Against the background of the isotropic model (1), a number of studies were carried out for the above modes generated by an analogue of the NDE [34]. Next, we found an analogue of the NDE for the mode $m=1$ and $N=3$ against the background of an anisotropic model using the method described in [34]:

$$\Lambda_{1\tau}(\Psi) = \frac{3}{8(1+\lambda \cos \Psi)^4} K_{13}^*(\Psi) (\lambda + \cos \Psi)^{2-\tau} \overline{\sin^{\tau} \Psi} \quad \overline{\tau = 0 - 2},$$

Here $K_{13}^*(\Psi) = \left[11q_1^2 - \frac{3}{2}q_3 \right] l_0(\Psi) + [25q_1q_2 \sin \Psi] l_1(\Psi) + \left[11q_3q_2 - \frac{3}{2}q_1^2q_2 \right] l_2(\Psi),$

$$q_1 = \lambda + \cos \Psi \quad q_2 = 1 - \lambda^2 \quad q_3 = q_2 \sin^2 \Psi. \tag{7}$$

It is known that the method used to create a composite model can also be used to find an analogue of the NDE against the background of a composite model. Using numerical calculation, we have constructed input diagrams for $v=0.0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75$ and 1 .

For the composite model (6) NDE for $m=1$ and $N=3$ takes a different form

$$\Lambda_{1\tau}(\Psi) = \frac{3}{8(1+\lambda \cos \Psi)^4} \cdot (v \cdot I_{13}^*(\Psi) + (1-v) \cdot K_{13}^*(\Psi)) \cdot (\lambda + \cos \Psi)^{2-\tau} \overline{\sin^{\tau} \Psi} \quad \overline{\tau = 0 - 2}.$$

Here: $I_{13}^*(\Psi) = [11q_1^2 + (5\Omega^2 - 4)q_3 - 10i\Omega q_1 \sqrt{q_2} \sin \Psi] l_0(\Psi) + [10(3 - \Omega^2)q_1q_2 \sin \Psi + 10i\Omega \sqrt{q_2}(q_1^2 - q_3)] l_1(\Psi) + [11q_3q_2 + (5\Omega^2 - 4)q_1^2q_2 + 10i\Omega q_1q_2^{3/2} \sin \Psi] l_2(\Psi)$ и $K_{13}^*(\Psi) = [11q_1^2 - \frac{3}{2}q_3] l_0(\Psi) + [25q_1q_2 \sin \Psi] l_1(\Psi) + [11q_3q_2 - \frac{3}{2}q_1^2q_2] l_2(\Psi),$

$$q_1 = \lambda + \cos \Psi \quad q_2 = 1 - \lambda^2 \quad q_3 = q_2 \sin^2 \Psi. \tag{8}$$

NDE (8) is a system of six second-order differential equations that cannot be analyzed analytically. But it is not difficult to perform numerical solutions [35, 36, 37]. The results of the numerical analysis of the NDE show that the plot of the dependence of the critical parameters of the initial virial ratio $(2T/|U|)_0$ on the rotation parameter Ω for the values of various superposition parameters $\nu=0. 0.25. 0.5. 0.75$ and 1 has a complex form:

Fig. 1. Dependences of the initial virial ratio on the degree of rotation for various values of the superposition parameter a) $\nu=0.25$ b) $\nu=0.5$ c) $\nu=0.75$.

It can be seen from the critical diagram (Fig. 1a) that in the structural model within the unstable region a stable field was formed with superposition parameters $\nu=0.25$ in the range $0.402 \leq \Omega \leq 0.601$ in terms of the rotation parameter. There is an instability zone $0.856 \leq (2T/U)_0 \leq 0.858$ and $0.620 \leq (2T/U)_0 \leq 0.622$. With the rotation parameter $\Omega=0.708$, if $0.509 \leq (2T/U)_0$, then the transition from an unstable field to a stable one begins. With the values of the rotation parameter $0 \leq \Omega \leq 0.02$ and

$0.735 \leq \Omega \leq 1$, according to our calculations, the oscillation amplitude is $\lambda \approx 0$. which corresponds to the instability of the equilibrium state [22–28].

If the superposition parameter is $\nu=0.5$ (Fig. 1b), then it can be seen that there is an oscillatory instability that occurs at values of the rotation parameter $\Omega=0, 0.006, 0.177$ ($0 \leq (2T/U)_0 \leq 0.419, 0.729 \leq (2T/U)_0 \leq 0.734$ and $0.836 \leq (2T/U)_0 \leq 0.839$). At $\Omega=0$ dynamic instability, if $0 \leq (2T/U)_0 \leq 0.654$. The critical diagram reaches extrema at the values of the rotation parameter $\Omega=0.05, 0.540, 0.74283$ and 0.74890 .

A dependence diagram was also obtained for the separation parameter $\nu=0.75$ (Fig. 1c). Here there is oscillatory instability at the values of the rotation parameter $\Omega=0, 0.028, 0.101, 0.699$ and ($0.515 \leq (2T/U)_0 \leq 0.612, 0.573 \leq (2T/U)_0 \leq 0.579, 0.419 \leq (2T/U)_0 \leq 0.421, 0.326 \leq (2T/U)_0 \leq 0.331$). At $\Omega=0$, a dynamic instability field appeared $0 \leq (2T/U)_0 \leq 0.412$. With the values of the rotation parameter $\Omega=0.115$ and 0.651 , the input diagram goes to extreme values. During this time, an instability island formed inside the stable sphere, reaching an extreme value at $\Omega=0.320$. Between the extreme values of the rotation parameter ($\Omega=0.651, 0.775$), a line formed that separates the stable field $0.348 \leq (2T/U)_0$ with the rotation parameter $\Omega=0.701$. This line reached its extreme point at $\Omega=0.693$.

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